

Yet Another Newsletter

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The profession of Library Service is undergoing through transformation & transition. In India it has started from the beginning of this Century. There is no denying however, that transformation is sort of an indicator of dynamism of an entity and our profession seems to be dynamic in this yardstick. The changing concepts of documents from books and Information to Knowledge Resources have certainly established the fact since long. The changes in the very nature of documents in both content & form warrant considerable transformations in the modalities in acquisition, organization, processing, repackaging & transmission of information *aka* knowledge resources. It is needless to mention that India has witnessed birth & growth of a pool of new generation of such knowledge industry professionals competent enough to compete with their western counterparts who had savoured the benefit of technology much ahead of us. These new-gen professionals are well aware of global activities in the state-of-the-art technologies in our field.

Amidst this scenario, viability of bringing out yet another Newsletter seems to be questionable to many among us. As the editor, I believe, it is my responsibility to explain the objective behind introducing the LIS Links Newsletter among the professionals in general & the LIS Links members in particular.

It is known that there exist sort of unevenness in knowledge capacity among members. Such unevenness are due to mainly two reasons. First, the individual's personal interest to (global) knowledge resources and second, is ones' better access to cyber media & infrastructure. It is a known fact that even junior staffs of institutions like IITs, AIIMS, IISERs or IIMs have far better infrastructure & cyber access than a Librarian in an average Degree College at suburb areas. It is a bare fact that the knowledge & skills of a quite promising and competent professional often gets rusty as he/she finds no choice but to take up employment in a school at remote area!

The newsletter is being introduced with a high hope to shorten the gap of knowledge & expertise among the members. It is aimed to act as a platform for them through which they can view the world more clearly and more closely. I appeal to all our members to come forward to bridge the gap existing among our co-professionals.

We shall feel our effort successful if all these individuals find it useful for them.